

Restoration of energy-efficient buildings from local raw materials

Orazbayev Sadiq

Faculty of Construction of the Karakalpak State University named after Berdaq:
Student of the course " Construction Materials and Constructions " ..

Annotation: the design of energy-efficient buildings requires the implementation of complex energy-saving measures. Energy-saving measures can only be implemented when economically feasible.

The criterion of economic feasibility is the minimum of incurred costs.

Keyword:energy,engineering systems, building blocks, semi-functional constructions, unconventional energy protection.

It is necessary to consider the main measures aimed at energy conservation in the operation of buildings. In the analysis of existing energy efficient buildings , retaining construction constructions can be optimized as follows:..

- the use of efficient heating multi-layer barriers and a small number of heat transfer devices;
- a structure protecting the outer and outer surfaces of the walls from moisture and the rational placement of layers of material in mult i-layered constructions.improving the humidity regime of barriers;
- installation of air-conditioning systems in outdoor heaters;
- improvement of the quality and construction of horizontal and vertical joints, which normally have a lower air penetration and heat dissipation;
- construction of semi
- functional structures, such as a wall that serves as an accumulator of heat energy; creation of a supporting structure, a heat accumulator and a low
- potential energy source; -optimization of the size of the lighting units; -increase in the number of lighting units;
- application of special types of lighting units (e.g., heat-retardant and heat-absorbing);
- enhancement of the use of sunscreen;.

Taking into account the climatic and natural characteristics of the construction area for optimization of architectural and planning solutions in the process of designing buildings. need to get. The main ways of implementing this principle are as follows:

- reducing the surface area of the building's exterior;
- insulating the building; - using stationary solar shades; World scientific research journal

- considering the possibility of windshields in the design of the floors, and windshield ventilation of the rooms in hot areas;
- rational placement of workstations and rooms..

Non-conventional energy includes primarily solar energy, geothermal energy, and low

-potential energy from the earth's crust..

The most promising ways to reduce the consumption of fuel and energy resources in the operation of buildings are:

- utilization of solar energy received by collectors installed on the roof of the building;
 - use of solar energy in a special device with a concentrator for the electrochemical conversion of heat, cold and electricity supply of buildings;
 - use of geothermal fluids for the provision of hot water and heating of buildings;
 - use of low-potential heat in the groundwater and soil part, i.e. using a heat pump installed in the soil (water) in an integrated heat exchanger to convert the low-potential heat in the soil and groundwater to the energy generated by the heat supply of water and heating of buildings;
 - use of solar energy by means of structures that utilize and accumulate water;
- the use of thin panels of sunscreen that convert solar energy into electricity;
- the use of bioenergetic resources in the production of methane fuel gas;
- the utilization of waste heat.

The improvement of engineering systems is aimed at solving two problems: rational energy use and maximum energy utilization (heat recovery).. The main ways to address this issue are: ??

Ventilation and air-heat recovery; ?? Wastewater recovery; ?? Use of periodic balancing devices; ?? Creation of local ventilation, lighting and cooling (conditioning) and heating systems; ?? Rational design of engineering systems that ensure compliance with microclimate parameters in each room. However , the four main energy-saving measures in buildings cannot be implemented without fulfilling the following conditions:

1 Condition ?? Mathematical modeling of energetic processes in buildings;

2 Condition ?? Implementation of an automatic system for controlling the microclimate and engineering systems of the building.

Energy supply system elements of buildings are essential. Therefore, when designing energy efficient buildings, all the building's engineering systems and construction constructions are taken into account. For example, you have to install a battery on the roof of a building to use solar energy, which puts extra weight on the building's structure and foundation. Due to the unstable nature of solar energy, an additional source of heat, such as a ground heat exchanger, should be considered. When designing external barriers, the maximum amount of heat loss in the building should not exceed the amount of heat received from the sun and soil. Otherwise, additional heat sources will have to be considered when designing energy efficient buildings. This means that the design of energy efficient buildings requires the implementation of complex measures aimed at energy saving. Energy-saving measures can only be implemented when economically feasible. The criterion of economic feasibility is the minimum of incurred costs. Indeed, this calculation holds true when the capital expenditures are calculated for the period of construction of the building, while the operating costs are calculated for the actual period of operation of the building. The problem is that there's no way to accurately predict the future cost of building materials, electricity, heat. Alternatively, the cost-benefit method can be used, but it has its own complexity and drawbacks. One of the major disadvantages is the cost of energy itself, which is the conversion of energy cost to labor cost. The most affordable energy-efficient exterior protective structures are multi-layer composite constructions of doors and walls made of mineral-efficient materials. The main reserves of heat saving can be used to insulate buildings against cold. Insulation of exterior walls is the most expensive and time-consuming process, which ensures a 10-15% reduction in heat transfer during winter seasons. The most widely used method of insulating exterior walls from cold includes ventilated constructions (styles), non-ventilated constructions of exterior walls with mineral and polystyrene foils directly fixed to the wall or frame, and a combination of these options using local heaters. The most efficient way of solving the problem in a complex way is by using the style insulation in the bricks of energy-efficient door and window blocks and roof structures. The mean value of the heat transfer resistance across the building R_{00} ?? it is determined using the following formula: where,

- the heat transfer resistance of the enclosed portions of the floor, window, roof,

and wall; ?? the surface area of the floor, window, roof, and wall.

Experiments show that high energy efficiency can be achieved by modernizing and introducing new energy-saving control instruments and equipment, energy sources, existing engineering systems in the operation of buildings.. The most important principles are: F of the cells in this room. I to. Increase in temperature, loss of heat waste in the district and main heat networks, modernization of the building's hot water supply and heating systems, regulation of the use of energy resources consumed in each apartment. F of shops in the kitchen. I to. Local steam boilers in the form of containers are installed on the roof of the building to reduce the need for long-distance heat networks. Modernization of heating systems will be carried out by switching to individual automated heat points with freely controlled quality and quantity. Establishment of daytime, nighttime, winter, spring and autumn heating regimes, alternate heating, thermal energy savings up to 20% Installation of heat meters (8-10%) and heating systems (10-12%) Installation of heat meters and meters (10-12%) Temporary increase in outside air temperature during the heating season of buildings Temperature can be adjusted in rooms between heating seasons. One of the main innovations in the improvement of heating systems in energy efficient residential buildings is the introduction of simultaneous air heating and cooling ventilation [16]. However, the total heat consumption of the building must provide the number of air passages in the standard air exchange and air heating system.. Calculations show that at a standard air exchange level, approximately 14 W/m² of heat can be covered using an air heating system.. Solving the problem of coordinating heat loss in different parts of the building (first, middle, and upper floors, corner locations) is of natural interest.. This problem can be solved by applying protective contractions to different thermal insulation layers ..

List of publications used.

1. Булгаков С.Н. Энергоэффективные строительные системы и технологии // Промышленное и гражданское строительство.- 1999.- №11.- С.20-23.
2. Изменчивость климата в Средней Азии.-Т.: САНИГМИ,1985.-Geog. fanlaridoktoriF.A. Muminovanashiriostida.-215b.
3. Суханов И.С. Лучистая энергия солнца и архитектура – Toshkent: «Фан», 1973. – 224 б.

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